

Southern California CSU DNP Consortium

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MANAGEMENT OF DIABETIC FOOT ULCER

A DOCTORAL PROJECT

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DOCTOR OF NURSING PRACTICE

By

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ABSTRACT

Many veterans with diabetes developed peripheral neuropathy, causing sensation loss to their toes or feet that leads to poor circulation; thus, minor injuries can lead to skin breakdown, ulcer formation, and subsequent infection (VA, 2017). Also, diabetes causes slower healing and a higher chance of infections that can potentially lead to amputation of the foot or part of the foot (VA, 2017). Although the known risk of developing diabetic foot ulcer (DFU) is high, there are no universal practice guidelines specifically addressing DFU. Hence, prompt attention and consistent management of DFU, using evidence-based clinical practice guidelines (CPG), is essential to improve outcomes of reduction or prevention of complications. For this project, an evidence-based CPG was adapted, implemented, and evaluated to improve the treatment and management of geriatric veterans with DFU in the transitional, inpatient care setting using Johns Hopkins evidenced-based practice (EBP) model.

In October 2019, a simple and easy-to-follow CPG algorithm of DFU was introduced to stakeholders, including Nurse Practitioners and Wound Care Consultant. A retrospective chart review was conducted two weeks post-implementation to assess adherence to CPG on pre-existing patients with DFU, followed by monthly chart review to evaluate ongoing adherence to the CPG. The evaluation was aimed at the adherence to the CPG for the following recommended practices: 1) Identifying patients with foot wounds, 2) implementing a clinical guideline for those who met the criteria, and 3)

assessing the status of foot wound healing as a long-term goal, which was not measured due to project limitation. The data showed 90 percent CPG adherence based on the ten patients that were identified with DFUs. Although evidence-based CPG has demonstrated improvement in patient safety and health outcomes, its utility and provider adherence vary among clinical settings and providers' discretion. A simple and easy-to-follow CPG algorithm can potentially promote adherence and facilitate implementation, and its consistent use eventually becomes a standard of practice.

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BACKGROUND

Diabetes accounted for the deaths of 30.3 million Americans and was known to be the 7th leading cause of death in the U.S. in 2015 (Centers for Disease Control and Prevention [CDC], 2017). Diabetes continues to be a growing health problem even though the rate of new diagnosis remains stable. Diagnosed diabetes increased at a rate of four percent among ages 18-44 years, 17 percent in ages 45-64 years, and 25 percent among ages 65 years and older (CDC, 2017). Acute and long-term complications associated with diabetes include premature death, stroke, heart disease, blindness, kidney disease, and amputations of toes, feet, or lower extremities. Chronic illness and limb loss are correlated with diabetes (Hingorani et al., 2016). Between 2006 to 2008, the incidence of diabetic foot ulcers was six percent among Medicare beneficiaries (Margolis et al., 2011). In the Medicare fee-for-service subpopulation with diabetes and peripheral vascular disease, the incidence of diabetic foot ulcers was 13.5 percent in 2006, 13.2 percent in 2007, and 13.1 percent in 2008 (Margolis et al., 2011). The average medical expenditures for individuals diagnosed with diabetes in 2012 were approximately \$13,700 per year, with \$7,900 attributed to diabetes (CDC, 2017).

Diabetes is prevalent among U.S. veterans due to a high incidence of obesity in this population. Diabetes affects nearly 25 percent of Veterans Affairs' (VA) patients and is known to be associated with blindness, renal disease, and amputation (U.S. Department of Veterans Affairs [VA], 2015). Many veterans with diabetes have neuropathy related to their illness, causing sensation loss to their toes or other parts of their feet that leads to poor circulation; therefore, minor injuries can lead to skin breakdown, ulcer formation, and subsequent infection without them noticing until the problem becomes serious (VA,

2017). Also, diabetes causes slower healing and a higher chance of infections that can potentially lead to amputation of the foot or part of the foot (VA, 2017). A diabetic foot ulcer (DFU) is defined as an ulcer usually occurring on the plantar aspect of the foot or over pressure points in patients with diabetes (London & Donnelly, 2000; Orneholm, Apelqvist, Larsson, & Eneroth, 2017). This severe outcome is especially challenging for older patients who often have other complications of diabetes, including kidney or heart disease.

In California, there are approximately 1.6 million veteran residents as of September 30, 2018 (VA, 2019). Of these veterans, 793,160 are aged 65 years and older, and 836,078 are 64 years and younger (VA, 2019). Further categorization of the veteran population revealed that there are approximately 133,056 veterans aged 65 and older residing in Los Angeles county and 56,792 living in Orange County (VA, 2019). There are nearly 134,982 and 48,156 veterans aged 64 years and younger who reside in Los Angeles and Orange counties, respectively (VA, 2019). Given the statistics, there is a significant number of veterans aged 65 years and older residing in Southern California, particularly in Los Angeles and Orange counties. A person age 65 years and older is often referred to as an “elderly” (World Health Organization [WHO], 2019).

There are three Veterans Healthcare Systems (VAHCS) serving veterans in Southern California, West Los Angeles, Long Beach, and San Diego. The Long Beach VA Healthcare System (LBVA), designated site for this project, includes five Community Based Outpatient Clinics (CBOCs), primarily serves veterans’ healthcare needs in Southern Los Angeles and Orange counties. LBVA is responsible for the care and services of over 56,000 veterans (VA, 2019). LBVA strives to create a culture of

engagement and continuous improvement through practices promoting teamwork and root cause problem-solving that enable LBVA staff to provide service excellence, in addition to fostering a culture of quality healthcare and constant readiness through performance improvement methods and sustainability (VA, 2019). LBVA also strives to obtain Magnet Status certification in two years and continually promotes evidence-based practice (EBP) by utilizing the Johns Hopkins Evidence-Based Practice Model.

Between October 1, 2016, and September 30, 2017, 4,564 veterans aged 65 years or older were admitted with a diabetes diagnosis, with or without comorbid conditions (CC), complications, or major complications (MCC) at the VA nationwide (VA, 2018). Forty-six veterans were admitted with diabetes, with or without CC or MCC, during the same year at the Long Beach VA (VA, 2018). Between October 1, 2017, and September 30, 2018, there were 4,854 veterans aged 65 years or older in all VAs nationwide, and 61 veterans at the Long Beach VA, admitted with diabetes diagnoses. This number was an increase of approximately 3% and 14%, respectively, in admissions with diabetes diagnosis with or without complications, compared to the previous year (VA, 2018). People with diabetes spend approximately 2.3 times higher than those people without diabetes on average medical expenditures (American Diabetes Association [ADA], 2018). The ADA (2018) reports that the cost of diabetes care increased by 26 percent from 2012 to 2017, particularly among adults aged 65 years and older.

The majority of veterans admitted to the VAHCS are from the Vietnam War era, age ranges from 55 to 97 years old with a mean age of 68 years old and are predominantly men [97%] (VA, 2017). Among veterans admitted to the LBVA with DFUs, some are unable to discharge home due to weight-bearing restrictions, requiring

some assistance with activities of daily living (ADLs), and lack of home support among other limitations. Therefore, they are referred and admitted to the Community Living Center (CLC), a transitional, skilled nursing, inpatient care unit. The veterans who are being served at the LBVA come from various demographical background including living status (i.e., homeless, renting a room, senior apartment, or own home), support system (i.e., living alone or with family), and functional level (i.e., independent, ambulatory with an assistive device, or wheelchair-dependent). VA resources are available to veterans if qualified includes, but not limited to, housing placement, service-connected benefits, and limited in-home caregiver support. The veterans who are generally admitted to the CLC require long-term intravenous antibiotic therapy for the treatment of osteomyelitis (bone infection complication from DFU), management of negative pressure wound therapy, and local wound care to DFU. The veterans' ability to perform wound dressing change or availability of home caregiver support are also considered.

Problem Statement

Given the prevalence of diabetes, several clinical practice guidelines have been published targeting effective management of the disease for the adult and elderly population, tailored mostly toward screening and general care and treatment, including glycemic or A1c (glycosylated hemoglobin) control, foot care, and eye care. However, no universal practice guidelines are addressing the complication of diabetic foot ulcers. The current standard of care supported by most practice guidelines include interprofessional management, patient education, glucose management, debridement (removal of damaged tissue), offloading, infection management, and adequate blood

supply (Braun et al., 2014). At the VA, a clinical guideline for diabetes management is available in the primary care setting for general care and treatment of type 2 diabetes (T2DM). An evidence-based CPG is needed for the management of diabetes with an associated DFU, particularly on the elderly veterans, to promote standardized, high-quality care, improve health outcomes, and reduce costs.

Purpose Statement

The goal of this project is to adapt, implement, and evaluate an evidence-based CPG to improve the treatment and management of elderly veterans with DFUs in the transitional, inpatient care setting. The objectives are to 1) review and appraise current practice clinical guidelines on DFU and its applicability to transitional, inpatient care setting; 2) modify or develop evidence-based CPGs; and 3) implement and evaluate its utility in the transitional, inpatient practice setting.

Supporting Framework

Evidence-based practice (EBP) has been recognized as a basis of standard clinical practice, aimed toward improving the treatment and management of diseases (Sullivan, Wayne, Patey, & Nasr, 2017). However, the translation of EBP to clinical practice is often slow due to barriers and organizational complexities, such as time constraints, resource limitations, poor-quality evidence, and lack of required skills (Sullivan et al., 2017).

A collaborative, integrative model is essential to interpret evidence into consistent, standardized practice in the transitional, inpatient care setting, such as using the Johns Hopkins Quality and Safety Research Group model (Pronovost, Berenholtz, & Needham, 2008). The Johns Hopkins model offers a collaborative approach,

emphasizing specific methods for translating evidence into practice, which ultimately provides proper care for the patient at the appropriate time, at all times, or each occurrence (Pronovost et al., 2008). The model identifies the problem within the broader healthcare system and engages cooperation from interprofessional teams centrally in stages one through three, and locally in stage four (Pronovost et al., 2008).

The Johns Hopkins Quality and Safety Research Group model is comprised of four stages: summarize, identify, measure, and ensure [Figure 1] (Pronovost et al., 2008). The first stage pertains to the summary of the evidence, including an appraisal of an existing guideline on diabetes with a foot ulcer in the transitional inpatient care setting, review of the literature to identify and confirm best practice, and team consensus on the implementation of the guideline with modifications. The second stage deals with local barriers to implementation including engagement of stakeholders to actively participate in the change process, attainment of perspective from all involved staff, and team evaluation of the structure and local context in the transitional inpatient care setting, hospital system policy (HSP), and standard operating procedure (SOP). The third stage includes measurement of the process or performance outcomes by obtaining baseline metrics, tracking ongoing metrics to assess if patients receive the recommended interventions, and following overall patient outcomes to evaluate improvement or effectiveness of the recommended intervention. The final stage ensures that all patients receive the appropriate treatment or intervention by implementing the “four Es” approach, comprised of engage, educate, execute, and evaluate, which highlights cultural change and staff engagement to improve consistency (Pronovost et al., 2008).

The first “E” is to engage providers and staff by explaining that the rationale for EBP clinical guideline is to provide consistent and standardized high-quality care and improve patients’ health outcomes. The second “E” is to educate all levels of staff in the transitional inpatient setting, by sharing evidence that supports best practice. The third “E” is to execute by designing and implementing a treatment or intervention “toolkit” targeted at the barriers, reminders, standardization, and learned mistakes. The final “E” is to evaluate by regularly assessing performance measures and unintended consequences, tracking metrics every three months, and sustaining a standardized, high-quality practice in the transitional inpatient care setting. Any change in practice or process cycles back to the first “E,” engage, and continues on a full circle until the intervention becomes part of routine practice.

Two additional Es were recently added, endure and extend, to integrate the project into the hospital’s quality improvement efforts, which includes obtaining resources to continue measurement and feedback of performance, dedicated time for teams to continue the work, and incorporating training on the intervention into staff orientation (Pronovost et al., 2008). The outcomes of this project may be expanded, utilized, and integrated into hospital-wide improvement efforts, and the training on the intervention will be incorporated into staff orientation.

Figure 1: John Hopkins Quality and Safety Research Group: Strategy for translating evidence into practice. Adaptation from Pronovost, P. J., Berenholtz, S. M., & Needham, D. N. (2008). Translating evidence into practice: A model for large scale knowledge translation. *British Medical Journal*, 377, a1714.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Overview

Alexiadou and Doupis (2012) defined diabetic foot ulcer (DFU) as a foot ulcer associated with peripheral nerve dysfunction (neuropathy) and peripheral arterial disease of the lower limb in patients with diabetes. London and Donnelly (2000), and Orneholm, Apelqvist, Larsson, and Eneroth (2017) defined DFU as an ulcer usually occurring on the plantar aspect of the foot or over pressure points in patients with diabetes. DFUs are associated with significant morbidity, mortality, and healthcare expenditures, and are common complications of diabetes mellitus (Everett & Mathioudakis, 2018; Strauss et al., 2016). Risk factors associated with development of DFUs include mechanical changes in bony structure of the foot, peripheral neuropathy, previous foot ulcerations, and atherosclerotic peripheral arterial disease (Amin & Doupis, 2016; Blakely, 2016; Lavery et al., 2016; Lew, Mills, & Armstrong, 2016; Hingorani et al., 2016; Morey-Vargas & Smith, 2015; Somayagi et al., 2017). These risk factors occur frequently and intensified in the diabetic population, and are often chronic (Amin et al., 2016; Blakely, 2016; Lavery et al., 2016; Lew et al., 2016; Hingorani et al., 2016; Morey-Vargas et al., 2015; Somayagi et al., 2017). DFUs require prolonged treatments since it takes longer to heal, and are often complicated by severe infections, hospital admissions, and amputation of feet and legs (Morey-Vargas et al., 2015; Strauss et al., 2016).

Limited Joint Mobility and Deformities

Morey-Vargas et al. (2015) and Strauss et al. (2016) claimed that the joint mobility limitation of the ankle and foot, and foot deformities could lead to foot susceptibility to abnormal high-pressure areas and limit the foot's capability to absorb

shock, subsequently increase ulceration risk. Strauss et al. (2016) identified claw, hammer, and mallet toes; bunions or rigid toes are deformities frequently observed in the diabetic foot structure. Other deformities include forefoot abduction/adduction, midfoot pronation/supination, equinus contracture (limited upward bending motion of the ankle joint) (Strauss et al., 2016). In the presence of these malformations, the plantar metatarsal heads and dorsal aspect of the toes are susceptible to repetitive trauma and extreme pressures, contributing to DFU delayed-healing (Morey-Vargas et al., 2015; Strauss et al., 2016). The foot is unable to provide adequate shock absorption in low joint mobility and unable to maintain normal plantar pressure, which can lead to trauma in the plantar surface resulting in foot ulceration (Zimny, Schatz, & Pfohl, 2004).

Diabetic Neuropathy

As one of the long-term complications of diabetes, neuropathy plays a central role in the development of foot ulcers (Morey-Vargas et al., 2015). Diabetic neuropathy involves evidence of peripheral nerve dysfunction in people with diabetes (Amin et al., 2016). Peripheral neuropathy (PN) predisposes the foot to ulceration due to its effects on the sensory loss interfering with the protective reaction to harmful stimuli (Blakely, 2016; International Best Practice Guidelines [IBPG], 2013). Motor neuropathy affecting the muscles of the foot, causing malformation and abnormal pressure over a bony prominence, while dry skin can result in cracking, fissures, and calluses due to associated autonomic neuropathy (Blakely, 2016; IBPG, 2013). The presence of PN is the initial factor in developing foot ulcers in patients with diabetes, even with minor trauma (Amin et al., 2016; Morey-Vargas et al., 2015). Patients' vulnerability to mechanical and thermal injuries increased when the protective sensation is lost due to sensory

neuropathy, increasing their risk of foot ulceration (Amin et al., 2016; Morey-Vargas et al., 2015). Amin et al. (2016) and Morey-Vargas et al. (2015) reported that muscle atrophy of the foot related to motor neuropathy can result in malformations such as hammertoes and protruding metatarsal heads, contributing to the evolution of abnormal areas of pressure, joint immobility, repetitive trauma, tissue damage, and subsequent ulcer formation.

Peripheral Arterial Disease

Peripheral arterial disease (PAD) is defined as the presence of blockage in the vasculature of the lower extremities, characterized by the intermittent claudication, aching pains or cramping that usually occurs in the calf muscles, as well as the thighs or the buttocks (Amin et al., 2016; Morey-Vargas et al., 2015; Turns, 2015). Pain may be present at rest in severe cases of PAD, and the extremity may show tissue loss or gangrene, known as critical limb ischemia (Amin et al., 2016; Turns, 2015).

Microvascular dysfunction, an alteration of the normal body reaction to foot ulcerations, can result in decreased perfusion and subsequently result in persistent non-healing foot ulcers (Amin et al., 2016; IBPG, 2013).

Standard of Care

The primary objective of DFU management is wound healing, specifically to treat DFU early to allow rapid healing and prevent progression or complications (IBPG, 2013). The vital components of management of DFU include treating underlying disease, local wound care with infection control, ensuring adequate blood supply, and pressure off-loading (Alexaidou et al., 2012; Amin et al., 2016; Everett et al., 2018; Hingorani et al., 2015; IBPG, 2013; Lavery et al., 2016). The most common treatment approach in the

19th century was bed rest; however, the management of DFUs was transformed by Dr. Frederick Treves (1853-1923) to comprise sharp removal of damaged tissue (debridement), off-loading, and diabetic foot education (Naves, 2013). Constructing from these principles, the current management of DFU includes local wound care with surgical or chemical debridement, wound dressings fostering a moist environment, off-loading, vascular evaluation, infection treatment, and glycemic management (Blakely, 2016; Braun, Fisk, Lev-Tov, Kirshner, & Isseroff, 2014; Everett et al., 2018; Hingorani et al., 2016; IBPG, 2013; Lavery et al., 2016; Turns, 2015).

Wound Debridement

Wound debridement of DFU is an essential step in the management of the wound, which involves removal of all damaged and unhealthy tissue impeding with healing, as well as peri-wound callus, which helps maintain healthy granular wound bed (Amin et al., 2016; Everett et al., 2018). Debridement includes surgical or sharp, enzymatic, mechanical, biological, or autolytic (Amin et al., 2016; Hingorani et al., 2016; Lavery et al., 2016). Teobaldi and Mantovani (2018) suggested that a sharp and major debridement may be reserved for the medial and lateral heel areas based on anatomic, biomechanical, and vascular knowledge, except in the presence of a critical lower limb ischemia; while a soft debridement may be specifically reserved for the central-posterior heel area.

Wound Dressings

Dressing products for diabetic foot wounds are recommended to preserve a moist occlusive environment for adequate wound healing, control drainage, and prevent maceration of peri-wound areas (Amin et al., 2016; Braun et al., 2014; Everett et al., 2018; Hingorani et al., 2016). A moist wound environment addresses multiple factors

affecting wound healing by creating a balanced wound environment, favoring cell migration, and matrix formation (IBPG, 2013; Lavery et al., 2016). A combination of wound dressings, off-loading, debridement, and infection control are used (Lavery et al., 2016).

Off-loading

Off-loading measures from DFU is an integral aspect of wound care, promoting healing and prevents ulcer recurrence, which can be attained by appropriate footwear, boots, and orthotic walkers (Everett et al., 2018; Hingorani et al., 2016). The location of the wound and the history of PAD will determine the modality of choice (Everett et al., 2018). Additional factors to consider before issuance of off-loading footwear includes the patient's preference, mobility, and capability to don and doff the footwear (Turns, 2015).

Vascular Assessment

Given that diabetes is one of the risk factors for PAD, early identification and medical management of PAD in patients with diabetes are vital given its contribution to poor healing or non-healing of DFU, higher amputation rates, and higher mortality rates (Everett et al., 2018; Hingorani et al., 2016; Naves, 2013). PAD is defined by Everett et al. (2018) and Morey-Vargas et al. (2015) as an ankle-brachial index (ABI) of less than 0.9, an ABI below 0.7 is associated with some level of arterial insufficiency, and an ABI less than 0.4 is associated with severe PAD. It is reported that there is a 50% risk in 2-year mortality if a patient suffers from an amputation with concurrent PAD and diabetes (Hingorani et al., 2016).

Infection Control

Since morbidity and mortality are associated with infections in DFUs, early recognition of the disease, and aggressive treatment is imperative in improving outcomes (Everett et al., 2018; IBPG, 2013). Infection ensues when there is an imbalance between bacteria and host defense favoring the bacteria, playing a pivotal role in the cause, healing, and complications of diabetic ulcers (Lavery et al., 2016). The Infectious Diseases Society of America (IDSA) recommends treating wounds when at least two signs or symptoms of infection are present, such as inflammation, including redness, warmth, swelling, tenderness, pain, induration, or pus-filled secretion, and may include secondary signs, such as non-purulent drainage, discolored tissue, tunneling of wound edges, or foul odor (Amin et al., 2016; Everett et al., 2018; Lipsky et al., 2012). Antibiotic therapy is not recommended if there are no signs of soft tissue or bone infection; however, a post-debridement specimen of infected wounds (preferably of a tissue) should be obtained to direct antibiotic therapy (Lavery et al., 2016; Lipsky et al., 2012). Narrow-spectrum antibiotics for the shortest duration is recommended to treat clinical diabetic foot infections to prevent antibacterial resistance and other adverse outcomes of antibiotic therapy, such as diarrhea or *Clostridium difficile* (Barwell et al., 2017; Lipsky, 2012).

Glycemic Control

Hemostasis, inflammation, proliferation, and remodeling are stages involved in wound healing (Guo & DiPietro, 2010). In a healthy state before an injury, the vasculature is in a balance in which blood vessels have an adequate blood supply to deliver sufficient nutrients and oxygen to the tissue (Okonkwo & DiPietro, 2017). In diabetes, the balance is significantly disturbed, disrupting wound healing, tissue

regeneration, and the repair of the healthy vasculature; thus, hyperglycemia, particularly in type 2 diabetes, has been linked to vascular disease progression (Okonkwo et al., 2017). Wound healing is significantly delayed in diabetes, promoting chronic non-healing ulcers attributed to the impact of insufficient angiogenesis (new blood vessel formation) and excessive neutrophil (white blood cell) infiltration associated with hyperglycemic environment (Lan, Wu, Huang, Wu, & Chen, 2013; Okonkwo et al., 2017). Nather, Cao, Chen, and Low (2018) found that patients with diabetes have inadequate comprehension regarding the disease and its management, and frequently present with a glycosylated hemoglobin (HbA1c) level of 10% or higher. An HbA1c target of 7% (53 mmol/mol) is a reasonable HbA1c for many nonpregnant adults (ADA, 2018). Some providers may suggest strict HbA1C targets (such as <6.5% [48 mmol/mol]) for specific patients if they can be accomplished without the adverse effect of hypoglycemia (ADA, 2018). Patients who may benefit from stricter HbA1c goals include diabetes of short duration, controlled type 2 diabetes with lifestyle management or metformin only, long life expectancy, or absence of cardiovascular disease (ADA, 2018). However, a systematic review by Fernando et al. (2016) yielded inconclusive results in determining whether intensive versus conventional glycemc management has a favorable or unfavorable outcome on foot ulcer treatment.

Multidisciplinary Approach

DFUs are a complex condition that are best evaluated and managed by an interprofessional team including, primary care providers, nurses, wound nurses, podiatrists, and subspecialties such as endocrinologists, orthopedic surgeons, vascular surgeons, orthotists, physical therapists, and others if resources are available (Everett et

al., 2018; IBPG, 2013; Internal Clinical Guidelines team, 2016; Morey-Vargas et al., 2015; Somayaji et al., 2017). However, there is no specific protocol adhered to by all departments, and it is unclear who should lead for continued, integrated care of patients across all settings (Cahn, Elishu, & Olshtain-Pops, 2014; Internal Clinical Guidelines team, 2016). Education in the diabetes care, foot care, and footwear choice should be directed at patients and caregivers, as well as primary care practitioners, doctors, nurses, and allied health professionals (Nather, Cao, Chen, & Low, 2018). Each interprofessional team member plays a pivotal role in the integrated approach. For example, a podiatrist or orthotist can provide custom-molded therapeutic footwear for deformities, while a surgeon might perform a surgical correction if deformities cannot be accommodated by therapeutic footwear (Morey-Vargas et al., 2015). A Physical Therapist provides exercise therapy that is vital to the maintenance of basic functioning and prevention of disability, adding to an essential role of lessening the negative factors involved in the evolution of diabetic foot (Francia et al., 2015). Patients with diabetes who are elderly and previously lived a sedentary lifestyle are often unable to perform physical activity (van Schie, 2008). Francia et al. (2015) posited that a decline in musculoskeletal fitness of diabetic patients associated with a disability might be reversible given improved mobility of the ankle joint, muscular strength, and walking performance after 12 weeks of tailored exercise therapy to the participant's condition.

Adjuvant Therapies

Adjuvant wound therapy is recommended if no improvement of DFUs, greater than 50% wound reduction, after a minimum of four weeks of standard wound therapy (Hingorani et al., 2015). Adjuvant therapies are divided into categories of topical agents,

devices focused on accelerating ulcer healing, and pharmacological methods for treatment (Everett et al., 2018; Lavery et al., 2016). The adjuvant therapy choice is determined based on clinical findings, treatment accessibility, and cost-effectiveness (Everett et al., 2018; Hingorani et al., 2015; Lavery et al., 2016).

Alginate and other dressings. Alginate dressings are derived from seaweed, come in the form of calcium alginate or calcium sodium alginate or alginic acid, which forms a highly absorbent gel that can absorb large volume of wound drainage to avoid skin maceration and still maintain a moist environment (Everett et al., 2018; Hingorani et al., 2015). Several agents that are currently being studied as topical antiseptic and antimicrobial agents for DFUs includes honey, a natural substance, thought to have antibacterial activity and other benefits due to its ability to draw fluid from surrounding vessels and provide a moist environment and topical nutrition (Everett et al., 2018; Hingorani et al., 2015).

Negative pressure wound therapy. Negative pressure wound therapy (NPWT) is a vacuum device that collects high volumes of wound drainage, reduces the frequency of dressing changes, keeps wounds clean, and reduces odor (Everett et al., 2018; Hingorani et al., 2015). Drumville et al. (2013) theorized that the vacuum forces aid in wound healing by increasing perfusion, extracting infectious material, and approximating wound edges.

Acellular bioproducts. Acellular dermal matrix (ADM) has been used for several years for wound healing, tissue repair, and reconstruction (Everett et al., 2018; Hingorani et al., 2015). Extracellular matrix plays a vital role in wound healing as it provides structural support and facilitates signals to control cellular responses (Guo, Mu, & Gao,

2017). Donor dermis that is decellularized retains bioactive agents and acts as a support for host cell repopulation, thought to aid in wound healing by promoting vascularization and providing a barrier to bacteria and a moist wound environment, which increases cell regeneration (Everett et al., 2018; Guo et al., 2017).

Risk Stratification

The presence of DFU places patients with diabetes at risk for amputation; thus, a rapid and appropriate assessment and classification of a DFU is a critical part of management (Amin et al., 2016; Morey-Vargas et al., 2015). Morey-Vargas et al. (2015) specified that the stratification systems established to predict foot ulceration risk was rooted in the increasing presence of risk factors for DFU development. Monteiro-Soares, Boyko, Ribeiro, Ribeiro, and Dinis-Ribeiro (2011) reported that the diabetic PN, PAD, foot deformities, and prior history of ulceration or amputation are considered as the main features in the majority of the risk stratification systems. Even in neuropathic patients considered at low-risk of ulceration, the plantar pressure distribution (PPD) can cause potentially dangerous alterations (Giacomozzi, Sartor, Telles, Uccioli, & Sacco, 2018). Although data shows that the utilization of risk stratification systems can be precise approaches for identifying patients at risk, their use has not been fully adopted by professional organizations due to their complexity in practical day-to-day use (Amin et al., 2016; Monteiro-Soares et al.; 2011; Morey-Vargas et al., 2015).

Clinical Practice Guidelines Adherence

Clinical practice guideline (CPG) development to circulate quality accessible evidence is intended to guide clinical practice, enhance high-quality care, and reduce inappropriate treatment or interventions for specific circumstances (Hall, Irish, Gregg,

Groome, & Rohland, 2015; Ryan, 2017). The organization group of the Society for Vascular Surgery, the American Podiatric Medical Association, and the Society for Vascular Medicine reviewed relevant existing guidelines and adapted several evidence-based recommendations to provide a general direction for the management of DFU (ADA, 2003; Hingorani et al., 2016; Lipsky et al., 2012). The Wound Healing Society (WHS) advisory panel was selected to update the 2006 DFU guidelines to assist clinicians in healthcare decision making, identify areas for further research, and simplify debatable diagnosis and treatment procedures (Lavery et al., 2016). The International Working Group on the Diabetic Foot (IWGDF) had published an updated international Practical Guidelines for the management of DFU since 1999 (Bakker, Apelqvist, Lipsky, & Van Netten, 2016). In the 2015 update, the name was changed to 'Guidance' from 'Practical Guidelines,' with the outcome of evidence-based global consensus on prevention and management of foot problems in diabetes (Bakker et al., 2016).

The development of CPGs is extensive and expensive, and understanding their impact in clinical practice is essential (Hall et al., 2015; Ryan, 2017). CPGs consolidate an immense quantity of evidence into focused and comprehensible statements designed for clinicians to enhance the quality of care delivered (Ryan, 2017). In the IWGDF Guidance document, robust data remains insufficient on who should be screened, screening tools to use, and when to appropriately screen for foot ulceration risk, in addition to the scarcity of high-quality data on the benefits of treatment or interventions preventing an initial foot ulcer (Bus et al., 2016). A variety of barriers impede dissemination and adherence to recommendations in CPGs (Cabana et al., 1999).

Lawton et al. (2015) posited that the primary motivator of prescribing patient-centered care and treatment was to fulfill patient needs, rather than absolute adherence to clinical guidelines. Although beliefs that CPG adherence certifies the quality of care, health and safety of the patient, the potential gains (e.g., decreased hospital admission or readmission) associated with CPG adherence were observed to offset the direct costs (e.g., increased consultation time, prescribing fees) (Lawton et al., 2015). Adherence to CPGs also alleviates potential consequences, enhancing practice reputation (Lawton et al., 2015). Other related barriers to CPG adherence include time constraints (e.g., up-to-date, relevant information with instructive activities), and lack of secondary care communication (e.g., transmission of prescription changes) (Lawton et al., 2015). Awareness of individual patient records was perceived as fundamental to patient care, whether medication or treatment was prescribed (Lawton et al., 2015).

Summary

It is noteworthy to mention that gaps in knowledge and practice continue to persist, despite the availability of current high-quality CPGs to guide standards of care in patients with DFUs in general, particularly in elderly age 65 years and older. Substantial research on the prevention or treatment of neuropathy is strongly needed as PN is considered a critical risk factor for the evolution of foot ulcers in patients with diabetes (Bus et al., 2016). Although the scope of DFU treatment currently being studied is promising, well-designed randomized controlled trials (RCTs) to determine the efficacy of interventions are lacking (Everett et al., 2018). The cost-effectiveness of any of the interventions have not been thoroughly investigated; therefore, more research attention to price is also necessary (Bus et al., 2016).

METHODS

This project aimed to adapt, implement, and evaluate an evidence-based CPG to improve the treatment and management of elderly veterans with diabetic foot ulcers in the transitional, inpatient care setting. The three specific project aims corresponded to the following questions: 1) Were the providers writing appropriate wound care orders based on the presenting status of the wounds? 2) Were the providers assessing for ischemia, infection, and neuropathy? and 3) Were the patients referred to the appropriate specialist?

To certify that all identified patients received appropriate treatment or interventions, the “four Es” approach, comprised of engage, educate, execute, and evaluate, were addressed. A plan was presented to engage stakeholders and dedicated staff with the change process in September 2019. A forum was arranged to obtain feedback. An on-unit educational in-service was provided to engage staff on EBP and addressed staff questions. During the execute phase, a CPG algorithm and a data collection tool to assess CPG adherence were developed (Appendices A, B). A retrospective chart review was conducted two weeks post-implementation of CPG to assess CPG adherence on pre-existing patients with DFU, followed by monthly chart review to evaluate ongoing CPG adherence. Data obtained was analyzed, and the findings were summarized. The pilot study findings were shared with stakeholders and involved staff.

Search Methods

An extensive literature review was completed for this evidence-based practice project. Searches for publications were performed utilizing the databases PubMed,

CINAHL, and Cochrane Library. Three relevant topics were searched: diabetic foot ulcer, standard of care or treatment, and clinical practice guidelines. Grey literature was also explored, including consensus or committee reports, and non-peer reviewed journals. A hand search of reference lists was also performed. Limits of the search included English-language studies on adults aged 65 years and older, from peer-reviewed journals published between 2014 and 2019. Articles excluded included those focused on diabetes but without foot ulcers, other diabetic complications such as amputation and foot infection, and children. Publications were further screened for the relevance of theme and duplication of studies. Medical subject headings (MeSH) and key terms were used, including diabetic foot ulcer, pressure ulcer, lower extremity, wound care, treatment or intervention or therapy, standard of care, clinical guideline, or clinical practice guideline. Sources of evidence found that were excluded, reviewed, and used are listed in Table 1-3.

Search Results

Table 1

Database: PubMed

Terms	Limits	Articles			
		Retrieved	Excluded	Reviewed	Used
Diabetes AND foot ulcer AND wound care	Peer-reviewed, English language, human subjects, date: 2014-2019, age: 65+ years	183	104	80	2
Diabetes AND foot ulcer AND standard of care	Peer-reviewed, English language, human subjects, date: 2014-2019, age: 65+ years	73	53	20	1
Clinical guidelines or clinical practice guidelines AND	Peer-reviewed, English language, human subjects, date:	24	15	9	3

diabetic foot ulcers	2014-2019, age: 65+ years				
Diabetes AND pressure ulcer AND lower extremity	Peer-reviewed, English language, human subjects, date: 2014-2019, age: 65+ years	4	2	4	3

Note: Articles excluded based on title, duplication, and relevance to the project topic

Table 2

Database: Cumulative Index of Nursing and Allied Health Literature (CINAHL)

Terms	Limits	Articles			
		Retrieved	Excluded	Reviewed	Used
Diabetes AND foot ulcer AND wound care	Peer-reviewed, English language, human subjects, date: 2014-2019, age: 65+ years	26	15	11	3
Diabetes AND foot ulcer AND standard of care	Peer-reviewed, English language, human subjects, date: 2014-2019, age: 65+ years	7	2	5	2
Diabetes AND foot ulcer AND clinical guidelines or clinical practice guidelines	Peer-reviewed, English language, human subjects, date: 2014-2019	5	2	3	3

Note: Articles excluded based on title, duplication, and relevance to the project topic

Table 3

Database: Cochrane Library

Terms	Limits	Articles			
		Retrieved	Excluded	Reviewed	Used
Diabetic foot ulcers	English language, date: 2014-2019	9	0	9	1

Note: Articles excluded based on title, duplication, and relevance to the project topic

Project Timeline

Data monitoring for this project comprised of retrospective chart reviews to determine if adherence to the implemented clinical guideline aimed at improving the management of DFUs were consistently followed.

February 2019	March 2019	April 2019	May 2019	June 2019	July 2019
Project purpose statement, initial TOE 2/10	Project supporting framework 3/10	ROL/TOE 4/14 Methods/evaluation plan 4/18	Spring semester ends	Summer semester begins	
			Present project to N695 class		Present plan to GEC HCG, obtain approval for data collection (support letter)
August 2019	September 2019	October 2019	November 2019	December 2019	January 2020
Fall semester begins				Fall semester ends	Spring semester begins
In-service staff on best practice Defend project proposal	Obtain IRB from CSUF Begin data collection (baseline data)	Partial implementation, current outcomes Chart review 2 weeks post-implementation	Monthly chart review	Monthly chart review	Monthly chart review Complete 4-month data analysis Write up analysis of data
February 2020	March 2020	April 2020	May 2020		
Paper revisions per TL/TM feedback	Ensure paper meets approval of committee, finalize paper, make poster. HHD Research presentation	WIN Poster Presentation at Portland, OR Dissemination Day	Finalize clinical hours log Graduation!		

Ethical Considerations

The project procedure was approved by the project site and the Institutional Review Board (IRB) of California State University, Fullerton (CSUF). Patient records were reviewed using the Computerized Electronic Patient Record System (CPRS). All

protected patient data was accessed following the Veterans Health Administration (VHA) institutional policies regarding access to the patient health information (PHI), supported by the use of a password and public key infrastructure (PKI) software. Data on patients who met the criteria as having DFUs were de-identified. All hard copy data that were collected were destroyed after analysis. It was anticipated that no harm ensued to the patients as this project comprised of retrospective chart review, and no patients were recruited.

Design

A post design was used. A retrospective chart review was conducted two weeks post-implementation to assess adherence to CPG on pre-existing patients with DFU, followed by monthly chart review to evaluate ongoing adherence to the CPG and results of this project. The evaluation aimed at the adherence to the CPG for the following recommended practices: 1) Identifying patients with foot ulcers, 2) implementing clinical guideline for those who met the criteria, and 3) assessing the status of foot wound healing as a long-term goal, which was not fully measured due to project limitation.

Operational Definitions

The operational definitions of the key variables for patient characteristics were as follows:

DFU defined as an ulcer usually occurring on the plantar aspect of the foot or over pressure points in patients with diabetes.

Wound healing defined as closure of the wound or decreasing wound size compared to presenting size of the wound.

Risk factors were defined as any captured documentation identified on the medical record problem list, including diabetes, neuropathy, Charcot arthropathy, joint deformities, and peripheral vascular disease.

Complications were defined as any captured documentation identified on the medical record, including infection, osteomyelitis, and amputation of any part of the foot.

Setting

The project was completed at a 75-bed transitional, inpatient care unit, situated annexed to the 350-bed national teaching healthcare system, serving both male and female veterans in Southern California. The transitional care unit was divided into short-term skilled nursing, dementia care, and hospice.

Sample

The records of male and female patients admitted with DFUs to the transitional, inpatient care unit between September 2019 to January 31, 2020 were included in the analysis. Patients were identified using sorted data from the CPRS. Records were excluded if lower extremity wounds were identified as vascular, venous stasis, or pressure wounds.

Data Collection

The Nurse Practitioner developed a data collection tool integrating input from the interprofessional team in July 2019 (Figure 3). All patients were assigned an identification number for added patient identity protection, and all rosters adhered to the institutional Health Insurance Portability and Accountability Act (HIPAA) regulations. All variables were collected on all patients, including demographics (age, gender, ethnicity, admission diagnosis, and risk factors for DFU), complicating factors

(peripheral vascular disease, infection, amputation), and a requirement for debridement or other surgical procedures.

Measures

Demographic data (age, gender, ethnicity, admission diagnosis) was measured categorically. Age was measured in years. Providers' adherence to CPG was measured using metric. Metric 1 was used to measure the number of CPG components meeting the criteria (numerator) compared to the total number of patients with DFUs (denominator).

Metric 1:
$$\frac{\text{number of CPG components meeting criteria}}{\text{Total number of patients with DFUs}}$$

Statistical Analysis

All data collected were entered and analyzed utilizing the QI Macros. Data were examined for accuracy of data entry, missing values, and frequencies and distributions before data analysis. Descriptive statistics were applied to analyze collected data answering the three questions posed regarding this project.

Evaluation

At the end of the project, a four-month chart review was performed to evaluate the providers' adherence to the CPG in the treatment and management of geriatric veterans with DFUs who were admitted to the transitional, inpatient care setting. The data analysis answered the three project questions: 1) Did the providers write appropriate wound care orders based on the presenting status of the DFUs? 2) Did the providers assess for ischemia, infection, and neuropathy? and 3) Were the patients referred to the appropriate specialist?

RESULTS

The results of this project were aimed at evaluating CPG adherence at four months post-implementation. Initial data were collected between October 17, 2019 to January 20, 2020 after implementation of the CPG in October 2019. Before implementation, stakeholders including Nurse Practitioners and Wound Care Consultant were educated on the CPG. A data collection process was placed. For this project, three questions were answered:

- 1) Did the providers write appropriate wound care orders based on the presenting status of the DFUs?
- 2) Did the providers assess for ischemia, infection, and neuropathy?
- 3) Were the patients referred to the appropriate specialist?

Question 1: Wound Care Orders

A daily roster of admitted patients to the transitional care unit was collected and reviewed. The patients with DFU who were admitted before CPG implementation were included. A chart review was conducted between October 17, 2019 to January 20, 2020. There were 141 patients, including previously admitted patients before CPG implementation. Of the 141, ten patients identified with DFUs were further reviewed. The wound care orders were tailored based on the presenting status of wound, as described in Table 4, and periodically changed based on wound changes or healing.

Table 4

Characteristics of Wound and Wound Care

Characteristics of foot/wounds on admission	N=10	Wound care
<i>Left lower extremity</i>		
Charcot arthropathy s/p midfoot wedge ostectomy, plantar foot ulcer	1	Cast, plantar foot ulcer cleanse with acetic acid, acetic-moistened gauze daily
calcaneal osteomyelitis s/p debridement of calcaneus and heel ulcer	1	Cleanse with NS, NPWT, amnion skin substitute on heel
Charcot arthropathy s/p correction, plantar ulcer	1	Cleanse with NS, cadexomer (iodosorb) daily
foot plantar ulcer	1	Cleanse with NS, bacitracin
3 rd -5 th toe osteomyelitis s/p 3 rd -5 th ray amputation, heel ulcer	1	Cleanse with NS, cadexomer daily
dorsal foot I&D and 5 th toe amputation	1	Cleanse with NS, collagenase (santyl), then bacitracin daily
<i>Right lower extremity</i>		
plantar ulcer	1	Cleanse with acetic acid, acetic-moistened gauze daily
great toe ulcer	1	Cleanse with NS, dry gauze daily
great toe ulcer s/p right TMA, heel ulcer	1	Cleanse with NS, gentian violet daily
heel ulcer	1	Cleanse with NS, cadexomer daily

Note: I&D = Incision and drainage/debridement, NPWT = Negative pressure wound therapy, NS = Normal saline, S/p = Status post, TMA = Transmetatarsal amputation

Question 2: Assessment of Ischemia, Infection, and Neuropathy

Of the ten patients, one was not assessed for ischemia. No ankle-brachial index or CT Angiography was performed. Whether further imaging or intervention was warranted, was based on wound changes or healing and clinical judgment on the part of the clinician, as depicted in Table 5. All patients with DFUs were followed by a multidisciplinary team including primary Nurse Practitioner, Wound Care Consultant, Orthopedic or Vascular, Nursing for continued wound care or dressing changes, Dietitian for nutritional optimization for wound healing, and Physical Therapy, Kinesiotherapy, or Occupational Therapy for appropriate therapeutic activities with off-loading measures as indicated.

Table 5

Assessment and Complications

N=10	Risk factors	Vascular assessment	Infection or Amputation	Debridement/surgical procedures
2	FD, DN	ABI (n=2)	None (n=2)	None (n=1) Debridement (n=1)
4	PVD, DN	Arterial US (n=1) ABI (n=2) CTA (n=1)	None (n=2) Infection (n=2)	Right first ray amputation, revision amputation, first MT resection (n=1) Debridement (n=1)
2	DN	No vascular assessment (n=1) Not indicated (n=1)	Infection (n=2) Amputation (n=1)	Right foot I&D, 3 rd TMA revision amputation and ex-fix placement (n=1)
1	FD	ABI (n=1)	None (n=1)	Right foot osteotomy, primary closure
1	FD, DN, PVD	ABI (n=1)	Infection (n=1)	Angioplasty, Right midfoot fusion and ex-fix placement

Note: ABI = Ankle-brachial index, CTA = CT Angiography, DN = Diabetic neuropathy, Ex-fix = external fixator, FD = Foot deformity, I&D = Incision and drainage/debridement, MT = Metatarsal, PVD = Peripheral vascular disease, TMA = Transmetatarsal amputation, US = Ultrasound.

Question 3: Referral to Specialist

All ten patients identified with DFU were followed by a specialist (i.e., Orthopedic or Vascular). One of the ten patients was initially followed by Vascular, where he underwent angioplasty to his right lower extremity and two weeks later, he underwent right midfoot fusion and external fixator placement by Orthopedic.

Table 6

Referral

Specialist	N=10 (%)
Orthopedic	6 (60%)
Vascular	3 (30%)
Orthopedic & Vascular	1 (10%)

DISCUSSION

The findings of this four-month QI project performed in a single inpatient, transitional care unit, showed that the CPG was effectively implemented for patients who were admitted with DFUs. The data yielded 90 percent CPG adherence based on the ten patients identified with DFUs. A simple and easy-to-follow CPG algorithm facilitated implementation and enhanced adherence. Although evidence-based CPG has shown improvement in patient safety and health outcomes, its utility and provider adherence vary among clinical settings and clinicians' discretion.

The characteristic of the DFUs upon presentation during admission determines the current status of the ulcer and its associated complications, including infection with or without surgical intervention. Approximately half of the DFUs are infected when patients present for care based on clinical exam (Boulton et al., 2018). When patients with DFUs were referred to the transitional care unit, their wounds had been stabilized, requiring continued wound care or intravenous antibiotic therapy. Chastain, Klopfenstein, Serezani, and Aronoff (2019) posited that osteomyelitis almost always results from an extension of infection from a chronic ulcer in patients with diabetic complications involving the foot and ankle. Clinicians should suspect osteomyelitis in patients with non-healing DFU in six weeks with appropriate antibiotic therapy and off-loading measures (Lipsky et al., 2012). No more than six weeks of antibiotic therapy is required for osteomyelitis with a residual infected bone (Uçkay, Berli, Sendi, & Lipsky, 2019), and one to two weeks of antibiotic therapy is sufficient for most mild to moderate soft-tissue infections (Lipsky et al., 2012).

The multidisciplinary approach enhanced team collaboration in the management of DFU, reducing further complications, and promoting wound healing. Although complete wound healing was not observed on this limited project, a long-term, prospective, clinic-based study of DFUs done by Fesseha et al. (2018) showed 77.1% (450 wounds) had evidence of wound healing based on complete epithelization, and 85.6% (411 wounds) were confirmed to have sustained wound closure at 6-week follow-up visits.

Limitations of the Project

As a pilot project conducted in a single inpatient transitional care unit, between October 2019 to January 2020, data collection was limited to geriatric patients with DFU. Among patients who were admitted ($n=141$), only ten patients were identified with DFUs. Although data on this project yielded promising results of 90 percent CPG adherence, a complete wound healing was not observed. Patient compliance with the treatment, including off-loading measures and reasonable glucose control, also contributed to overall patient outcomes. Caution is advised in interpreting the result of this project, given the small sample size conducted on a specific population.

Strengths of the Project

The strength of this project was the use of an integrative framework to adapt a CPG aimed at effective treatment and management of DFU. The John Hopkins Quality and Safety Framework, a collaborative implementation model, translating knowledge into practice was appropriate for this project. The model encouraged the engagement of stakeholders, the involvement of the multidisciplinary team, and local collaboration. The engagement of clinicians and nursing staff in closely monitoring wound changes

prompted notification of specialists, including orthopedic, vascular, or podiatry. Translating evidence is a complex and challenging task on its own. Adapting EBP requires a multilevel approach in the healthcare organization. Collaborative teamwork provided a supportive, nonjudgmental environment that improved communication and trust.

Implications in Nursing Practice and Research

Nurses serving at the forefront of patient care are almost always the first clinician to interact with patients. The critical element of effective treatment and management of a patient with DFUs involves nursing. As a result of this project, patient education, thorough skin or wound assessments, and collaborative team approach is highly recommended to promote better patient outcomes and potential cost-containment. Nurses play vital roles in assessing patients for appropriate therapy and providing timely interventions. Knowledge of current EBP is crucial in the effective treatment and management of DFUs to prevent further complications and promote wound healing, as DFUs had been associated with reduced life expectancy, 5-year mortality rates of as high as 55% for ischemic ulcers and 77% for those with a previous lower limb amputation (Fortington et al., 2013).

Further research is needed to evaluate the long-term impact of a consistent, evidence-based standard of care for geriatric patients with a DFU, including the cost of innovative treatments and interventions. An emphasis on a multidisciplinary approach to treatment and management should become a standard of practice to reduce complications, promote better patient outcomes, and cost-containment. Even though the scope of DFU treatment currently being studied is promising, well-designed randomized controlled

trials (RCTs) to determine the efficacy of interventions are lacking (Everett et al., 2018). The cost-effectiveness of any of the interventions have not been thoroughly investigated; therefore, more research attention to price is also necessary (Bus et al., 2016). Further research on the prevention or treatment of neuropathy is strongly needed as PN is considered a critical risk factor for the evolution of foot ulcers in patients with diabetes (Bus et al., 2016).

Conclusions

Diabetes-related foot complications have been identified as the single most common cause of morbidity among diabetic patients (Lim, Ng, & Thomas, 2017). DFU is a dreaded complication of diabetes, given their high risk of infection and amputation (Fesseha et al., 2018). The complicating factor of underlying PVD and PN diminishes the majority of DFUs symptoms until the evidence of non-healing ulcers become evident (Lim et al., 2017). Prudent health care clinicians must consistently follow evidence-based CPG for the benefit of the patients and overall long-term health outcomes unless extenuating circumstances are preventing its utilization on either part of the clinicians or the patients.

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APPENDIX A

Figure 2: Algorithm of DFU Management. ABI = Ankle-brachial index; DFU = diabetic foot ulcer; HBO = hyperbaric oxygen; MRI = magnetic resonance imaging; NPWT = negative pressure wound therapy; PAD = peripheral arterial/vascular disease; PTB = probe to bone; XR = radiography. Adaptation from Hingorani, A., LaMuraglia, G., Henke, P., Meissner, M., Loretz, L., Zinszer, K.,... & Murad M. H. (2016). The management of diabetic foot: A clinical practice guideline by the Society for Vascular Surgery in collaboration with the American Podiatric Medical Association and the Society for Vascular Medicine. *Journal of Vascular Surgery*, 63(2S), 3S-21S. doi:10.1016/j.jvs.2015.10.003

APPENDIX B

Data Collection Tool

APPENDIX C**MANUSCRIPT SUBMITTED TO
*JOURNAL OF STAFF DEVELOPMENT IN NURSING*****ABSTRACT**

Individuals with diabetes developed peripheral neuropathy, causing sensation loss to their toes or feet that leads to poor circulation; thus, minor injuries can lead to skin breakdown, ulcer formation, and subsequent infection. Diabetes also causes slower healing and a higher chance of infections that can potentially lead to amputation of the foot or part of the foot. Prompt attention and consistent management of diabetic foot ulcers, using evidence-based clinical practice guidelines, is essential to improve outcomes of reduction or prevention of complications. A simple, evidence-based, and easy-to-follow clinical practice guideline algorithm of diabetic foot ulcers was introduced to stakeholders in the transitional, inpatient care setting using Johns Hopkins evidenced-based practice model. The evaluation was aimed at the adherence to the clinical practice guideline for the following recommended practices: 1) Identifying patients with foot wounds, 2) implementing a clinical guideline for those who met the criteria, and 3) assessing the status of foot wounds. The data showed 90 percent of clinical practice guideline adherence based on the ten patients that were identified with diabetic foot ulcers. The utility of clinical practice guidelines and provider adherence vary among clinical settings and providers' discretion despite the evidence of demonstrated improvement in patient safety and health outcomes. A simple and easy-to-follow clinical practice guideline algorithm can potentially promote adherence and facilitate implementation, and its consistent use eventually becomes a standard of practice.

BACKGROUND

Diabetes was the seventh leading cause of death in the U.S. in 2015, accounting for the deaths of 30.3 million Americans, 9.4 percent of the U.S. population (Centers for Disease Control and Prevention [CDC], 2017). Diagnosed diabetes increased at a rate of four percent among adults ages 18-44, 17 percent in adults ages 45-64 years, and 25 percent among ages 65 years and older (CDC, 2017). Acute and long-term serious complications associated with diabetes include premature death, heart disease, stroke, vision loss, kidney failure, and amputations of toes, feet, or lower extremities. Diabetes is one of the leading causes of chronic disease and limb loss (Hingorani et al., 2016).

Diabetes is prevalent among U.S. veterans due to a high incidence of obesity in this population, affecting nearly 25 percent of Veterans Affairs' (VA) patients and is known to be associated with blindness, renal disease, and amputation (U.S. Department of Veterans Affairs [VA], 2017). Many veterans with diabetes have neuropathy related to their illness, causing sensation loss to their toes or other parts of their feet that leads to poor circulation; therefore, minor injuries can lead to skin breakdown, ulcer formation, and subsequent infection without them noticing until the problem becomes serious (VA, 2017). Diabetes also causes slower healing and a higher chance of infections that can potentially lead to amputation of the foot or part of the foot (VA, 2017). A diabetic foot ulcer (DFU) is defined as an ulcer usually occurring on the plantar aspect of the foot or over pressure points in patients with diabetes (Orneholm, Apelqvist, Larsson, & Eneroth, 2017). This severe outcome is especially challenging for older patients who often have other complications of diabetes, including kidney or heart disease. The ADA (2018) reports that the cost of diabetes care increased by 26 percent from 2012 to 2017,

particularly among the population aged 65 years and older, contributing to the growing economic cost to the Medicare program.

Problem Statement

Given the prevalence of diabetes, several clinical practice guidelines have been published targeting effective management of the disease for the adult and elderly population, tailored mostly toward screening and general care and treatment, including glycemic or A1c (glycosylated hemoglobin) control, foot care, and eye care. However, no universal practice guidelines are addressing the complication of DFU. Multidisciplinary management, patient education, glucose control, debridement, off-loading, infection control, and adequate perfusion are the mainstays of the standard of care endorsed by most practice guidelines (Braun et al., 2014). At the VA, a clinical practice guideline (CPG) for diabetes management is available in the primary care setting for general care and treatment of type 2 diabetes. An evidence-based CPG is needed for the management of diabetes with associated DFU to promote standardized, high-quality care, improve health outcomes, and reduce costs.

Purpose Statement

The aim of this project is to adapt, implement, and evaluate an evidence-based CPG to improve the treatment and management of elderly veterans with DFUs in the transitional, inpatient care setting. The objectives are to 1) review and appraise current practice clinical guidelines on DFU and its applicability to transitional, inpatient care setting; 2) modify or develop evidence-based CPGs; and 3) implement and evaluate its utility in the transitional, inpatient practice setting.

Supporting Framework

Evidence-based practice (EBP) has been identified as a foundation of mainstream clinical practice, aimed toward improving the treatment and management of diseases (Sullivan, Wayne, Patey, & Nasr, 2017). However, the translation of EBP to clinical practice is often slow due to barriers and organizational complexities, such as time constraints and resource limitations, general poor-quality evidence, lack of required skills, and a culture that continues to rely on apprenticeship style of teaching (Sullivan et al., 2017).

A collaborative, integrative model is essential to translate evidence into consistent, standardized practice in the transitional, inpatient care setting using the Johns Hopkins Quality and Safety Research Group model (Pronovost, Berenholtz, & Needham, 2008). The Johns Hopkins Quality and Safety Research Group model offers a collaborative approach, emphasizing specific methods for translating evidence into practice, which ultimately provides appropriate care for the patient at the appropriate time, at all times, or each occurrence [Figure 1] (Pronovost et al., 2008). This model highlights the problem within the broader healthcare system and engages collaborative, multidisciplinary teams centrally, in stages one through three, and locally in stage four (Pronovost et al., 2008).

The Johns Hopkins Quality and Safety Research Group model is comprised of four stages: summarize, identify, measure, and ensure (Pronovost et al., 2008) (Figure 1). The first stage contains the summary of the evidence, including the appraisal of an existing guideline on diabetes with a foot ulcer in the transitional inpatient care setting, review of the literature to identify and confirm best practice, and team consensus on the implementation of the guideline with modifications.

The second stage addresses local barriers to implementation, including engagement of stakeholders to participate in the change process actively, attainment of perspective from all involved staff, and team evaluation of the structure and local context in the transitional inpatient care setting, hospital system policy (HSP), and standard operating procedure (SOP).

The third stage includes measurement of the process or performance outcomes by obtaining baseline metrics, tracking ongoing metrics to assess if patients receive the recommended interventions, and tracking overall patient outcomes to determine improvement or effectiveness of the recommended intervention.

The final stage ensures that all patients receive the appropriate interventions by implementing the “four Es” approach, engage, educate, execute, and evaluate, which highlights cultural change, contextual factors, and staff engagement, to improve reliability (Pronovost et al., 2008).

The first E is to *engage* providers and staff by explaining that the rationale for EBP clinical guidelines is to provide consistent and standardized high-quality care and improve patients’ health outcomes. The second E is to *educate* all levels of staff in the transitional inpatient setting, by sharing evidence that supports best practice. The third E is to *execute* by designing and implementing an intervention “toolkit” targeted at the barriers, reminders, standardization, independent checks, and learned mistakes. The final E is to *evaluate* by regularly assessing performance measures and unintended consequences, tracking metrics every six months, and sustaining a standardized, high-quality practice in the transitional inpatient care setting. Any change in practice or process cycles back to the first E, *engage*, and continues on the full circle until the

intervention becomes part of routine practice. Two additional Es were recently added, *endure* and *extend*. The outcomes of this project may be extended, utilized, and integrated into hospital-wide improvement efforts, and the training on the intervention will be incorporated into staff orientation.

Figure 1: John Hopkins Quality and Safety Research Group: Strategy for translating evidence into practice. Adaptation from Pronovost, P. J., Berenholtz, S. M., & Needham, D. N. (2008). Translating evidence into practice: A model for large scale knowledge translation. *British Medical Journal*, 377, a1714.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

An extensive literature review was completed for this EBP project. Searches for publications were performed utilizing the databases PubMed, CINAHL, and Cochrane

Library. Three relevant topics were searched: diabetic foot ulcer, standard of care or treatment, and clinical practice guidelines. Grey literature was also used, including consensus or committee reports, and non-peer reviewed journals. A hand search of reference lists was also performed. Limits of the search included English-language studies on adults aged 65 years and older, from peer-reviewed journals, published between 2014 and 2019. Articles excluded included those focused on diabetes but without foot ulcers, other diabetic complications such as amputation and foot infection, and children. Publications were further screened for the relevance of theme and duplication of studies. Medical subject headings (MeSH) and key terms were used, including diabetic foot ulcer, wound care, treatment or intervention or therapy, standard of care, clinical guideline or clinical practice guideline. Sources of evidence found were listed in Table 1-3.

Table 1

Database: PubMed

Terms	Limits	Articles			
		Retrieved	Excluded	Reviewed	Used
Diabetes AND foot ulcer AND wound care	Peer-reviewed, English language, human subjects, date: 2014-2019, age: 65+ years	183	104	80	2
Diabetes AND foot ulcer AND standard of care	Peer-reviewed, English language, human subjects, date: 2014-2019, age: 65+ years	73	53	20	1
Clinical guidelines or	Peer-reviewed, English language,				

clinical practice guidelines AND diabetic foot ulcers	human subjects, date: 2014-2019, age: 65+ years	24	15	9	3
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Note: Articles excluded based on title, duplication, and relevance to the project topic

Table 2

Database: Cumulative Index of Nursing and Allied Health Literature (CINAHL)

Terms	Limits	Articles			
		Retrieved	Excluded	Reviewed	Used
Diabetes AND foot ulcer AND wound care	Peer-reviewed, English language, human subjects, date: 2014-2019, age: 65+ years	26	15	11	3
Diabetes AND foot ulcer AND standard of care	Peer-reviewed, English language, human subjects, date: 2014-2019, age: 65+ years	7	2	5	2
Diabetes AND foot ulcer AND clinical guidelines or clinical practice guidelines	Peer-reviewed, English language, human subjects, date: 2014-2019	5	2	3	3

Note: Articles excluded based on title, duplication, and relevance to the project topic

Table 3

Database: Cochrane Library

Terms	Limits	Articles			
		Retrieved	Excluded	Reviewed	Used

Diabetic foot ulcers	English language, date: 2014-2019	9	0	9	1
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Note: Articles excluded based on title, duplication, and relevance to the project topic

Alexiadou and Doupis (2012) defined diabetic foot ulcer (DFU) as a foot ulcer associated with peripheral nerve dysfunction (neuropathy) and peripheral arterial disease of the lower limb in patients with diabetes, usually occurring on the plantar aspect of the foot or over pressure points (Orneholm, Apelqvist, Larsson, and Eneroth, 2017). DFUs are associated with significant morbidity, mortality, and healthcare expenditures, and are common complications of diabetes mellitus (Everett & Mathioudakis, 2018; Strauss et al., 2016). Risk factors associated with the development of DFUs include mechanical changes in the bony structure of the foot could lead to foot susceptibility to abnormal high-pressure areas and limit the foot's capability to absorb shock, subsequently increase ulceration risk; peripheral neuropathy which predisposes the foot to ulceration due to its effects on the sensory loss interfering with the protective reaction to harmful stimuli; and previous foot ulcerations, and atherosclerotic peripheral arterial disease causes blockage in the vasculature of the lower extremities (Amin & Doupis, 2016; Blakely, 2016; Lavery et al., 2016; Lew, Mills, & Armstrong, 2016; Hingorani et al., 2016; Somayagi et al., 2017). These risk factors occur frequently and intensified in the diabetic population, and are often chronic (Amin et al., 2016; Blakely, 2016; Lavery et al., 2016; Lew et al., 2016; Hingorani et al., 2016; Somayagi et al., 2017). DFUs require prolonged treatments since it takes longer to heal, and are often complicated by severe infections, hospital admissions, and amputation of feet and legs (Morey-Vargas et al., 2015; Strauss et al., 2016).

The primary objective of DFU management is wound healing, specifically to treat DFU early to allow rapid healing and prevent progression or complications (IBPG, 2013). The vital components of current management of DFU include local wound care with surgical or chemical debridement, wound dressings fostering a moist environment, off-loading, vascular evaluation, infection treatment, and glycemic management (Blakely, 2016; Everett et al., 2018; Hingorani et al., 2016; Lavery et al., 2016).

METHODS

This project aimed to adapt, implement, and evaluate an evidence-based CPG to improve the treatment and management of elderly veterans with DFUs in the transitional, inpatient care setting. The three specific project aims corresponded to the following questions: 1) Were the providers writing appropriate wound care orders based on the presenting status of the wounds? 2) Were the providers assessing for ischemia, infection, and neuropathy? and 3) Were the patients referred to the appropriate specialist?

The project procedure was approved by the project site and the Institutional Review Board (IRB) of California State University, Fullerton (CSUF). Patient records were reviewed using the Computerized Electronic Patient Record System (CPRS). All protected patient data was accessed following the Veterans Health Administration (VHA) institutional policies regarding access to the patient health information (PHI), supported by the use of a password and public key infrastructure (PKI) software. Data on patients who met the criteria as having DFUs were de-identified. All hard copy data that were collected were destroyed after analysis. It was anticipated that no harm ensued to the patients as this project comprised of retrospective chart review, and no patients were recruited.

A retrospective chart review was conducted two weeks post-implementation of CPG to assess adherence on pre-existing patients with DFU, followed by monthly chart review to evaluate ongoing adherence to the CPG and the results of this project. The evaluation aimed at the CPG adherence for the following recommended practices: 1) Identifying patients with foot ulcers, 2) implementing a clinical guideline for those who met the criteria, and 3) assessing the status of foot wound healing as a long-term goal, which was not fully measured due to project limitation.

The project was completed at a 75-bed transitional, inpatient care unit, situated annexed to the 350-bed national teaching healthcare system, serving both male and female veterans in Southern California. The transitional care unit was divided into short-term skilled nursing, dementia care, and hospice.

The records of male and female patients admitted with DFUs to the transitional, inpatient care unit between September 2019 to January 31, 2020, were included in the analysis. Patients were identified using sorted data from the CPRS. Records were excluded if lower extremity wounds were identified as vascular, venous stasis, or pressure wounds.

The Nurse Practitioner developed a data collection tool integrating input from the interprofessional team in July 2019. All patients were assigned an identification number for added patient identity protection, and all rosters adhered to the institutional Health Insurance Portability and Accountability Act (HIPAA) regulations. All variables were collected on all patients, including demographics (age, gender, ethnicity, admission diagnosis, and risk factors for DFU), complicating factors (peripheral vascular disease, infection, amputation), and a requirement for debridement or other surgical procedures.

Demographic data (age, gender, ethnicity, admission diagnosis) was measured categorically. Age was measured in years. Providers' adherence to CPG was measured using a metric. Metric 1 was used to measure the number of CPG components meeting the criteria (numerator) compared to the total number of patients with DFUs (denominator).

$$\text{Metric 1: } \frac{\text{number of CPG components meeting criteria}}{\text{number of patients with DFUs}}$$

RESULTS

The results of this project were aimed at evaluating CPG adherence at four months post-implementation. Initial data were collected between October 17, 2019 to January 20, 2020 after implementation of the CPG in October 2019. Before implementation, stakeholders, including Nurse Practitioners and Wound Care Consultant, were educated on the CPG. A data collection process was placed. For this project, three questions were answered:

- 1) Did the providers write appropriate wound care orders based on the presenting status of the DFUs?
- 2) Did the providers assess for ischemia, infection, and neuropathy?
- 3) Were the patients referred to the appropriate specialist?

Question 1: Wound Care Orders

A daily roster of admitted patients to the transitional care unit was collected and reviewed. The patients with DFU who were admitted before CPG implementation were included. A chart review was conducted between October 17, 2019 to January 31, 2020.

There were 141 patients, including previously admitted patients before CPG implementation. Of the 141, ten patients identified with DFUs were further reviewed. The wound care orders were tailored based on the presenting status of wound, as described in Table 4, and periodically changed based on wound changes or healing.

Table 4

Characteristics of Wound and Wound Care

Characteristics of foot/wounds on admission	N=10	Wound care
<i>Left lower extremity</i>		
Charcot arthropathy s/p midfoot wedge osteotomy, plantar foot ulcer	1	Cast, plantar foot ulcer cleanse with acetic acid, acetic-moistened gauze daily
calcaneal osteomyelitis s/p debridement of calcaneus and heel ulcer	1	Cleanse with NS, NPWT, amnion skin substitute on heel
Charcot arthropathy s/p correction, plantar ulcer	1	Cleanse with NS, cadexomer (iodosorb) daily
foot plantar ulcer	1	Cleanse with NS, bacitracin
3 rd -5 th toe osteomyelitis s/p 3 rd -5 th ray amputation, heel ulcer	1	Cleanse with NS, cadexomer daily
dorsal foot I&D and 5 th toe amputation	1	Cleanse with NS, collagenase (santyl), then bacitracin daily
<i>Right lower extremity</i>		
plantar ulcer	1	Cleanse with acetic acid, acetic-moistened gauze daily
great toe ulcer	1	Cleanse with NS, dry gauze daily
great toe ulcer s/p right TMA, heel ulcer	1	Cleanse with NS, gentian violet daily
heel ulcer	1	Cleanse with NS, cadexomer daily

Note: I&D = Incision and drainage/debridement, NPWT = Negative pressure wound therapy, NS = Normal saline, S/p = Status post, TMA = Transmetatarsal amputation

Question 2: Assessment of Ischemia, Infection, and Neuropathy

Of the ten patients, one was not assessed for ischemia. No ankle-brachial index or CT Angiography was performed. Whether further imaging or intervention was warranted, was based on wound changes or healing and clinical judgment on the part of the clinician,

as depicted in Table 5. All patients with DFUs were followed by a multidisciplinary team, including primary Nurse Practitioner, Wound Care Consultant, Orthopedic or Vascular, Nursing for continued wound care or dressing changes, Dietitian for nutritional optimization for wound healing, and Physical Therapy, Kinesiotherapy, or Occupational Therapy for appropriate therapeutic activities with off-loading measures as indicated.

Table 5

Assessment and Complications

N=10	Risk factors	Vascular assessment	Infection or Amputation	Debridement/surgical procedures
2	FD, DN	ABI (n=2)	None (n=2)	None (n=1) Debridement (n=1)
4	PVD, DN	Arterial US (n=1) ABI (n=2) CTA (n=1)	None (n=2) Infection (n=2)	Right first ray amputation, revision amputation, first MT resection (n=1) Debridement (n=1)
2	DN	No vascular assessment (n=1) Not indicated (n=1)	Infection (n=2) Amputation (n=1)	Right foot I&D, 3 rd TMA revision amputation and ex-fix placement (n=1)
1	FD	ABI (n=1)	None (n=1)	Right foot osteotomy, primary closure
1	FD, DN, PVD	ABI (n=1)	Infection (n=1)	Angioplasty, Right midfoot fusion and ex-fix placement

Note: ABI = Ankle-brachial index, CTA = CT Angiography, DN = Diabetic neuropathy, Ex-fix = external fixator, FD = Foot deformity, I&D = Incision and drainage/debridement, MT = Metatarsal, PVD = Peripheral vascular disease, TMA = Transmetatarsal amputation, US = Ultrasound.

Question 3: Referral to Specialist

All ten patients identified with DFU were followed by a specialist (i.e., Orthopedic or Vascular). One of the ten patients was initially followed by Vascular when he underwent angioplasty to his right lower extremity, and two weeks later, he underwent right midfoot fusion and external fixator placement by Orthopedic.

Table 6

Referral

Specialist	N=10 (%)
Orthopedic	6 (60%)
Vascular	3 (30%)
Orthopedic & Vascular	1 (10%)

DISCUSSION

The findings of this four-month QI project performed in a single inpatient, transitional care unit, showed that the CPG was effectively implemented for patients who were admitted with DFUs. The data yielded 90 percent CPG adherence based on the ten patients identified with DFUs. A simple and easy-to-follow CPG algorithm facilitated implementation and enhanced adherence. Although evidence-based CPG has shown improvement in patient safety and health outcomes, its utility and provider adherence vary among clinical settings and clinicians' discretion.

The characteristic of the DFUs during admission determines the current status of the ulcer and its associated complications, including infection with or without surgical intervention. Approximately half of the DFUs are infected when patients present for care based on clinical exam (Boulton et al., 2018). When patients with DFUs were referred to the transitional care unit, their wounds had been stabilized, requiring continued wound care or intravenous antibiotic therapy. Chastain, Klopfenstein, Serezani, and Aronoff (2019) posited that osteomyelitis almost always results from an extension of infection from a chronic ulcer in patients with diabetic complications involving the foot and ankle. Clinicians should suspect osteomyelitis in patients with non-healing DFU in six weeks with appropriate antibiotic therapy and off-loading measures (Lipsky et al., 2012). Six weeks of antibiotic therapy is required for osteomyelitis with a residual infected bone (Uçkay, Berli, Sendi, & Lipsky, 2019), and one to two weeks of antibiotic therapy is sufficient for most mild to moderate soft-tissue infections (Lipsky et al., 2012).

The multidisciplinary approach enhanced team collaboration in the management of DFU, reducing further complications, and promoting wound healing. A complete wound healing was not observed on this limited project. However, a long-term, prospective, clinic-based study of DFUs done by Fesseha et al. (2018) showed 77.1% (450 wounds) had evidence of wound healing based on complete epithelization, and 85.6% (411 wounds) were confirmed to have sustained wound closure at 6-week follow-up visits.

As a pilot project conducted in a single inpatient transitional care unit, between October 2019 to January 2020, data collection was limited to geriatric patients with DFU. Among patients who were admitted ($n=141$), only ten patients were identified with DFUs. Although data on this project yielded promising results of 90 percent CPG adherence, a complete wound healing was not observed. Patient compliance with the treatment, including off-loading measures and reasonable glucose control, also contributed to overall patient outcomes. Caution is advised in interpreting the result of this project, given the small sample size conducted on a specific population.

The strength of this project was the use of an integrative framework to adapt a CPG aimed at effective treatment and management of DFU. The John Hopkins Quality and Safety Framework, a collaborative implementation model, translating knowledge into practice was appropriate for this project. The model encouraged the engagement of stakeholders, the involvement of the multidisciplinary team, and local collaboration. The participation of clinicians and nursing staff in closely monitoring wound changes

prompted notification of specialists, including orthopedic, vascular, or podiatry.

Translating evidence is a complex and challenging task on its own. Adapting EBP requires a multilevel approach in the healthcare organization. Collaborative teamwork provided a supportive, nonjudgmental environment that improved communication and trust.

Implications in Nursing Practice and Research

The critical element of effective treatment and management of a patient with DFUs involves nursing. As a result of this project, patient education, thorough skin or wound assessments, and collaborative team approach is highly recommended to promote better patient outcomes and potential cost-containment. Nurses play vital roles in assessing patients for appropriate therapy and providing timely interventions. Current EBP knowledge is crucial in the effective treatment and management of DFUs for the prevention of further complications and the promotion of wound healing. DFUs had been associated with reduced life expectancy, 5-year mortality rates of as high as 55% for ischemic ulcers and 77% for those with a previous lower limb amputation (Fortington et al., 2013).

Further research is needed to evaluate the long-term impact of a consistent, evidence-based standard of care for geriatric patients with a DFU, including the cost of innovative treatments and interventions. An emphasis on a multidisciplinary approach to treatment and management should become a standard of practice to reduce complications, promote better patient outcomes, and cost-containment. Even though the scope of DFU

treatment currently being studied is promising, well-designed randomized controlled trials (RCTs) to determine the efficacy of interventions are lacking (Everett et al., 2018). The cost-effectiveness of any of the interventions have not been thoroughly investigated; therefore, more research attention to price is also necessary (Bus et al., 2016). Further research on the prevention or treatment of neuropathy is strongly needed as PN is considered a critical risk factor for the evolution of foot ulcers in patients with diabetes (Bus et al., 2016).

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APPENDIX D

AUTHOR GUIDELINES FOR JSDN

Journal for Nurses in Professional Development

Online Submission and Review System

<http://edmgr.ovid.com/jnsd/accounts/ifauth.htm>

Editorial Objectives

The *Journal for Nurses in Professional Development* is the official publication of the Association for Nursing Professional Development (ANPD) and is designed for professional development educators as a source of information on (1) planning, implementing, and evaluating professional development and inservice educational activities; (2) administration of professional development or inservice education departments; (3) research; (4) technological and other innovations; (5) issues in professional development and/or inservice education; and (6) patient education.

Editorial Policy

Manuscripts are considered for publication if they are submitted only to this journal and the author has not published similar topics elsewhere. One author should be the primary contact. The journal is not responsible if a manuscript is lost. Authors should keep a copy of their manuscript.

Submission of Manuscript

Online manuscript submission: All manuscripts must be submitted online through the new Web site at <http://www.edmgr.com/jnpd/>. **First-time users:** Please click the Register button from the menu above and enter the requested information. On successful registration, you will be sent an e-mail indicating your user name and password. *Note:* If you have received an e-mail from us with an assigned user ID and password, or if you are a repeat user, do not register again. Just log in. Once you have an assigned ID and password, you do not have to re-register, even if your status changes (that is, author, reviewer, or editor). **Authors:** Please click the log-in button from the menu at the top of the page and log in to the system as an Author. Submit your manuscript according to the author instructions. You will be able to track the progress of your manuscript through the system. If you experience any problems, please contact us through the "Contact Us" tab along the top of every page of the submission site.

Manuscript Preparation

Leave one-inch margins and use double-spacing throughout (including tables, figures, and references). Do not justify text.

Number the pages at the upper right from the first page of the text to the end of the references. The preferred length of a manuscript is 12-16 pages including figures, tables, and references.

Add line numbers to the entire manuscript before submitting.

Also include the following:

An **abstract** of the article (approximately 50-75 words) that gives an overview of the article and *clearly states the specific benefits* of the article for staff development educators. Do not cite references in the abstract. Spell out abbreviations and acronyms.

Author Biography. Include full name followed by suitable abbreviations for both professional licenses and the highest degree earned; honorary degrees in order of bestowal; professional or occupational title; and current position.

EXAMPLE: Marci J. Smith, MSN, RN, is Director of Staff Development at Memorial Hospital, Anytown, USA.

Title Page. Submit this page as a separate file when you are instructed to attach files to your submission. Include the title of the article and the author's name, preferred address, telephone number, fax number, and e-mail address. Author identification should appear *only* on the title page of the manuscript.

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References, Tables, and Figures

Use the *Publication Manual of the American Psychological Association, Seventh Edition, 2020*, for style and format guidelines.

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1. Learn about the publication requirements for Digital Artwork:
<http://links.lww.com/ES/A42>
2. Create, Scan and Save your artwork and compare your final figure to the Digital Artwork Guideline Checklist (below).

3. Upload each figure to Editorial Manager in conjunction with your manuscript text and tables.

B) Digital Artwork Guideline Checklist

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- Artwork should be saved as TIFF, EPS, or MS Office (DOC, PPT, XLS) files. High resolution PDF files are also acceptable.
- Crop out any white or black space surrounding the image.
- Diagrams, drawings, graphs, and other line art must be vector or saved at a resolution of at least 1200 dpi. If created in an MS Office program, send the native (DOC, PPT, XLS) file.
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Remember:

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- Number figures in the figure legend in the order in which they are discussed.
- Upload figures consecutively to the Editorial Manager web site and enter figure numbers consecutively in the Description field when uploading the files.

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We performed many tests on the degrees of flexibility in the elbow (see Video, Supplemental Digital Content 1, which demonstrates elbow flexibility) and found our results inconclusive.

- **List of Supplemental Digital Content**

A listing of Supplemental Digital Content must be submitted at the end of the manuscript file. Include the SDC number and file type of the Supplemental Digital Content. This text will be removed by our production staff and not be published.

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